

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF INFORMATION SECURITY POLICIES IN ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

This article analyzes the process of developing and implementing information security (IS) policies within organizations. The role of such policies in data protection and reducing cyber threats is examined. A step-by-step approach to implementation is explored, including risk analysis, goal setting, employee training, and monitoring. The importance of complying with regulatory requirements to minimize legal risks is emphasized. Key challenges, such as costs and the shortage of qualified specialists, are discussed.

Keywords: information security (IS), cyber threats, data protection, regulatory requirements, international cooperation.

Introduction

In light of the increasing number and complexity of cyber threats, information security (IS) has become an essential component of strategic management for any organization. Data breaches, confidentiality violations, and attacks on management systems lead to serious financial, legal, and reputational consequences. This creates a need for a systematic approach to developing and implementing IS policies aimed at reducing risks and ensuring the protection of information resources. IS policies consist of rules and procedures that regulate the actions of employees and partners regarding the use, storage, and protection of data. Developing such policies requires not only a deep understanding of the organization's internal infrastructure but also compliance with external regulatory requirements, which have become stricter in recent years. Policy development is a multi-step process that includes threat analysis, defining security objectives, creating regulatory documents, and assigning responsibilities. Equally important is the implementation stage, which involves monitoring, control, and adapting policies to changing conditions. Despite growing awareness of the importance of these measures, not all organizations implement comprehensive IS policies. This article aims to analyze the stages of policy development and implementation, identify key barriers to their realization, and review practices that enhance data protection effectiveness.

Main part. Theoretical foundations for developing IS policies

The increasing role of information in political processes demands scientific analysis. The emergence of new threats requires searching for strategies to ensure

IS. National interests in the information sphere are similar across the world: observance of constitutional rights and freedoms in the field of information; information support of state policy; development of modern information technologies; and protection of information resources from unauthorized access. However, unlike the USA, in many other countries this process is complicated by factors such as multinational and multi-confessional populations, the uneven spread of innovations, and other aspects [1]. IS in organizations is **not only about data protection** but also represents a holistic management process that includes risk assessment, creation of regulatory documents, and policy enforcement.

In the USA, organizational IS is regulated by laws such as the **Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act (GLBA)**, which governs the collection and processing of financial information; the **Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA)**; the **Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX)**; and requirements from the **National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)**. These regulations require organizations to adhere to data security standards, establish protective measures, and conduct regular audits. Globally, IS standards are primarily regulated by the ISO/IEC 27001 international standards, widely used as a benchmark for developing and implementing IS policies. According to a 2022 report by the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, the USA is shifting from «deterrence by denial» to «deterrence by punishment» in cyberspace, seeking greater resilience through the integration of the public and private sectors [2]. Developing an IS policy involves several key steps (table 1).

Table 1

IS policy development		
Stage number	Stage name	Description
1	Identifying needs and risk analysis	Assessment of the information infrastructure, identifying vulnerabilities, analyzing threat levels and probabilities.
2	Defining policy objectives	Setting IS objectives that align with business goals: confidentiality, availability, data integrity, and regulatory compliance.
3	Developing regulatory documents	Creating standards and guidelines for employees on data handling, storage, and transmission, taking industry requirements into account.
4	Assigning responsibility	Allocating roles and responsibilities among employees to ensure effective implementation of the security policy.

Each stage is significant not only as part of the overall system but also when evaluated independently – this requires a responsible approach to each step in the strategy. According to Statista, in 2023, 46% of USA respondents indicated that security monitoring and analytics are part of their cybersecurity strategy. Other methods include threat analysis and incident detection and response, noted by 38% and 37% of respondents, respectively. This highlights that both the human factor and technological assessment are essential for a comprehensive cybersecurity approach [3].

Stages of implementing IS policies

First stage in implementing IS policies is **fostering a culture of security awareness among employees**. Since human error is a common cause of security breaches, comprehensive training programs are essential. These programs educate staff on security rules, data handling procedures, and protocols for responding to potential threats. In addition, simulated phishing attacks and regular assessments reinforce knowledge and preparedness, helping employees recognize and avoid common cyber threats. Ensuring that all staff are informed and vigilant creates a collective responsibility for data protection and reduces the likelihood of accidental security breaches. **Establishing robust monitoring and control systems as next stage** is critical for maintaining compliance and security within an organization. This stage involves implementing regular checks to ensure that security policies are being followed and that any potential vulnerabilities are promptly identified. Automated control systems, including data processing tools, are frequently employed to detect suspicious activity and assess ongoing compliance. These systems can proactively block potential threats, alert security teams, and maintain real-time

data security. Regular audits and system checks are also instrumental in identifying areas where policies may need to be updated, as they provide insights into current security performance and areas for improvement. Finally, **risk management** is a strategic element in the development of IS policies, providing a structured approach to assessing and addressing potential threats. This stage involves identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing risks, allowing organizations to implement appropriate controls and minimize the impact of security incidents. In this process, policies are continuously reviewed and adjusted to keep pace with evolving cyber threats and changing organizational needs. Regular assessments and scenario planning allow organizations to remain proactive, adapting security measures to meet the latest risks and regulatory standards. According to Cisco, 52% of American companies experience data breaches within a year, and over 65% of companies surveyed by Cisco acknowledge that data privacy issues significantly delay the sales process [4].

Despite the importance of data protection, many organizations face barriers to implementing IS policies. One such barrier is the lack of financial resources: according to Deloitte, small companies allocate less than 3% of their budget to IS, making them particularly vulnerable. There is also a staffing challenge: finding highly specialized, qualified employees is a difficult task in any modern field. The U.S. Government and the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency are discussing funding for IT and security to encourage workforce growth, among other initiatives [5]. Additionally, cultural differences and national standard variations complicate collaboration for global corporations operating across different countries (pic. 1).

Pic. 1. SWOT-analysis of implementation of IS systems

The development and implementation of IS policies in organizations bring substantial advantages, contributing to a robust defense against cyberattacks, data breaches, and other security threats. These policies help minimize vulnerabilities by establishing guidelines for secure data handling, employee access controls, and incident response protocols. In addition, they ensure compliance with regulatory standards, which is increasingly critical as governments and industry bodies worldwide introduce stricter data protection regulations, such as GDPR in Europe and CCPA in California. By meeting these compliance requirements, companies not only avoid legal penalties but also build trust with customers and partners, enhancing their corporate reputation and demonstrating a commitment to data privacy and security.

However, implementing IS policies also presents considerable challenges. One of the primary drawbacks is the **high cost** associated with developing, deploying, and maintaining robust security frameworks. Organizations often need to invest in advanced cybersecurity tools, infrastructure upgrades, and ongoing monitoring to ensure resilience against sophisticated attacks. This investment can be especially burdensome for small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) with limited budgets. Another significant challenge is the **shortage of skilled IS professionals**. Cybersecurity is a rapidly evolving field, and the demand for qualified experts outstrips supply, leading to hiring difficulties and higher salaries. Moreover, the **human factor** remains a persistent vulnerability; employees may inadvertently introduce risks by ignoring security protocols, falling for phishing schemes, or mishandling sensitive data.

In addition to these challenges, there are promising opportunities for enhancing IS policies and practices. Technological advancements, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, are transforming cybersecurity by enabling automated threat detection and response, which can identify anomalies and respond to incidents more swiftly than manual methods. Furthermore, employee training and awareness programs are proving to be effective in strengthening organizational security. By educating staff on common

threats and safe practices, companies can reduce the likelihood of human error and reinforce a culture of security.

The outlook for IS policies in organizations continues to evolve. By 2026, Gartner predicts that 70% of boards of directors will include a member with cybersecurity expertise, reflecting the growing recognition of cybersecurity as a critical component of corporate governance [6]. To succeed in developing and implementing this technology, a comprehensive approach with dynamic risk management and scenario planning is essential [7].

Different approaches to implementing IS vary depending on the size and nature of the organization. Large corporations like Microsoft and IBM, IS is an independent division, which employ strategies based on comprehensive risk management and regular audits. The adoption of best practices in IS, such as threat detection systems, firewalls, and regular software updates, also helps reduce the likelihood of attacks [8].

Ultimately, the successful implementation of IS policies depends on a balanced approach that combines technological innovation, skilled personnel, and a strong organizational culture around security. Continuous improvement is vital, as new threats emerge regularly, and security needs change. Organizations that proactively adopt IS best practices, invest in employee training, and leverage advanced technologies are better equipped to protect their data, maintain compliance, and stay competitive in today's digital landscape.

Conclusion

Developing and implementing IS policies are critical elements for protecting data and ensuring organizations' resilience in the face of growing cyber threats. As the study shows, successful implementation of such policies requires a phased approach, from risk analysis and goal setting to employee training and regular monitoring. Regulatory compliance is important, minimizing the legal and financial risks associated with breaches of security standards. However, despite the clear benefits, the implementation process comes with significant challenges. The main challenges include high costs, lack of skilled professionals and the need to

constantly update policies to adapt to new threats. This is especially true for small and medium-sized companies, where security resources are limited. Global experience shows the high effectiveness of international cooperation and implementation of advanced technologies in cybersecurity. These areas represent important opportunities to optimize the security of organizations in a global environment. Thus, creating a flexible and adaptable IS policy becomes a necessity for modern organizations. Reliable IS builds trust from customers and partners, increasing the competitiveness and sustainability of the business in the long term.

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